

PRACTICES APPLIED BY GRADE 6 EDUCATORS IN FOSTERING HIGHER-ORDER THINKING SKILLS (HOTS) IN SCIENCE FOR 21ST-CENTURY SKILLS AT SAN NARCISO DISTRICTS, DIVISION OF QUEZON

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills at San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon. The study utilized the descriptive method and was conducted in San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon. It involved 20 school heads, 39 Grade 6 teachers, and 634 Grade 6 pupils sampled through purposive sampling. A questionnaire assessed Grade 6 educators' practices, revealing that the indicators are often applied. Moreover, a HOTS-based summative assessment evaluated Grade 6 pupils' performance in Science, showing that the Grade 6 pupils in the 20 schools, did not meet expectations. Furthermore, a simple linear regression analysis was performed to distinguish whether the independent variable influenced the dependent variable. The results revealed that the independent variable (practices applied by Grade 6 educators) does not statistically significantly affect the dependent variable (performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science). Thus, an intervention program has been developed based on the study's findings that introduce new practices to empower educators with innovative strategies and tools to foster critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving abilities among Grade 6 pupils.

Keywords: *Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS), 21st-century skills, Learning and innovation skills, Information, media, technology skills, Life and career skills*

INTRODUCTION

Thinking and other non-cognitive skills are becoming increasingly critical due to the information explosion, which places less emphasis on memorizing facts and more on understanding, analyzing, applying, evaluating, and creating. The cognitive domain encompasses lower-order thinking skills (LOTS) and higher-order thinking skills (HOTS), categorizing thinking into two main types. The first three levels of Bloom's taxonomy are memory, comprehension, and application. In other words, HOTS represents the pinnacle of Bloom's cognitive domain taxonomy. Fostering HOTS is crucial for student's educational success, emphasizing the need for teachers to have a deep understanding of HOTS and practical teaching and learning strategies.

Recent trends in education have emphasized the development of an individual's potential and skills across various subjects and disciplines. Thinking skills are recognized as crucial abilities necessary to navigate the information explosion, where relying solely on memory may not be sufficient to absorb vast knowledge. While knowledge acquisition remains a fundamental goal of education, there is also a growing recognition of the importance of enhancing other cognitive skills and competencies, particularly higher-order thinking skills, at various levels (Qasrawi & Beni Abdelrahman, 2020).

Theresia (2020) emphasized the increasing importance of higher-order thinking skills in the 21st-century education era. HOTS are elucidated within the cognitive domain, encompassing knowledge and intellectual skills. Teachers play a crucial role in nurturing these diverse domains of knowledge to facilitate high-level thinking among students. Possessing questioning skills is identified as an essential ability for teachers to enable students to engage in high-level thinking.

Cultivating student's higher-order thinking abilities has emerged as a central focus of educational curricula. The transfer of knowledge related to higher-order thinking from teachers to students can equip the latter with essential attributes for the 21st century. It is recommended that fostering awareness and mastery of the elements of higher-order thinking skills can benefit teachers and students. Teachers are urged to adopt creative and innovative teaching methods to provide students with opportunities to demonstrate their knowledge, skills, and abilities in acquiring 21st-century life skills (Singh et al., 2023).

Furthermore, educational systems worldwide emphasize the importance of fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) to prepare students for the new challenges of the 21st century. Some pressing issues faced by educators include the ambiguity of the construct, the implementation of HOTS in classroom practices, and the implications for teaching students from linguistically and culturally diverse backgrounds.

In line with this, an analysis was conducted on integrating 21st-century skills in the Philippines to assist the country in formulating a strategy for assessing, teaching, and learning these skills. This project was informed by several recent studies and national initiatives emphasizing the necessity for varied approaches in integrating 21st-century

skills to foster higher-order thinking skills among Filipino learners in 21st-century education (Scoular, 2020).

Furthermore, recent findings from the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) indicate that students in the Philippines continue to rank among the lowest globally in math, reading, and science. The latest test scores reveal no significant improvement in the country's performance since 2018. The findings highlight that only 23% of Filipino students reached basic proficiency in Science, suggesting that just one out of four students in PISA 2022 possessed the skills to recognize correct explanations for familiar scientific phenomena and validate conclusions (Chi, 2023).

With this background, the researcher aims to examine the different practices that Grade 6 educators apply in fostering HOTS in Science for 21st-century skills. The findings of this study can serve as a reference or benchmark for other schools in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills.

Research Questions

This study investigated the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills at San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills at San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon, in terms of:
 - 1.1. learning and innovation skills;
 - 1.2. information, media, and technology skills;
 - 1.3. life and career skills?
2. What is the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science?
3. Are the practices applied by Grade 6 educators significantly affecting the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science?
4. What intervention program could be introduced to address the identified gaps based on the study's findings?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher employed the descriptive research method, which involves recording, describing, interpreting, analyzing, and comparing events. This method was utilized to identify the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills at San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon.

Research Locale

The research took place in San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon. The two districts that represent San Narciso, Division of Quezon are San Narciso I and San Narciso II. Situated in the southeastern part of Quezon Province, it falls under the third congressional district of the province.

Statistically, according to the Divisional Monitoring and Evaluation Adjustment Program (DMEPA), most schools in San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon, failed to meet the division's target of a 75% Mean Percentage Score (MPS) across all learning areas. This statistical data underscores the urgent need for intervention to enhance educational outcomes in these districts. Consequently, the researcher felt compelled to conduct the study in this area, to identify factors contributing to low academic performance and propose effective interventions to address these issues.

Research Population and Sample

From the local study area, all elementary schools were included in the research population. Purposive sampling was employed to select school heads, teachers, and pupils from this population. This approach allowed for the deliberate selection of school heads, teachers, and pupils who possessed particular characteristics pertinent to the study's focus. By employing purposive sampling, the research aimed to capture a diverse range of perspectives and experiences, thus enhancing the richness and depth of the data collected. The population and sample of school heads consisted of 20 individuals. In contrast, the overall teaching personnel population tallied 313, with a corresponding sample size of 39, which was meticulously selected to ensure representation of critical characteristics pertinent to the study's objectives. In parallel, the student population enrolled amounted to 8,239, with an initially intended sample size of 634. However, due to student absences, the retrieved sample was reduced to 510.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire validated by the experts in the field. The survey instrument served as the primary tool for data gathering to secure reliable and primary data. The questionnaire comprised the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century

skills such as Learning and Innovation Skills; Information, Media, and Technology Skills; and Life and Career Skills. Respondents were asked to rate the indicators using a 5-point Likert Scale below.

Five-point Likert Scale

Scale	Mean Interval	Description	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.20-5.00	Always Applied	100% applied
4	3.40-4.19	Often Applied	75-99% Applied
3	2.60-3.39	Sometimes Applied	50-74% Applied
2	1.80-2.59	Poorly Applied	25-49% Applied
1	1.00-1.79	Almost Not Applied	0-24% Applied

The researcher-made questionnaire underwent validation by four experts in the field, including two Public Schools District Supervisors, one school head, and one master teacher. Following the validation process, the instrument was pre-administered to several school heads and teachers possessing characteristics similar to the study respondents. A reliability test was subsequently conducted, demonstrating the internal consistency and reliability of the instrument. The computed Cronbach’s Alpha for the research instrument for Grade 6 educators was 0.965, interpreted as Excellent.

Moreover, the researcher utilized a 50-item HOTS-based summative assessment to measure the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science. The assessment tool was adapted and modified from the Self-Learning Modules (SLMs) of Grade 6 for the 2nd quarter, along with a corresponding table of specifications. Additionally, the summative assessment underwent validation. Initially, the instrument received validation from the experts in the field as mentioned earlier. Following their approval, it was pre-administered to a sample of pupils with similar characteristics to the study respondents for pilot testing. Subsequently, an item analysis was conducted to determine reliability after retrieving the sample test.

Furthermore, the researcher indicated the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science using the grading scale and its corresponding descriptors outlined in DepEd Order No. 08 s. 2015 entitled “Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program”

Descriptors and Grading Scale

Descriptors	Grading Scale
Outstanding	100% applied
Very Satisfactory	75-99% Applied
Satisfactory	50-74% Applied
Fairly Satisfactory	25-49% Applied
Did Not Meet Expectations	0-24% Applied

Data Gathering Procedure

The study has two phases: the utilization of a survey questionnaire for Grade 6 educators and the utilization of summative assessment for the Grade 6 pupils.

Phase 1: Utilization of Survey Questionnaire

The researcher requested approval from the concerned school heads and teachers through letters approved by the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Quezon. Copies of these letters were then reproduced and personally distributed to the identified respondents. An explanatory letter accompanied the survey instrument, providing instructions on how to fill it out. Additionally, the researcher explained the questionnaire and guided the respondents. They were given a specific time to complete the questionnaire, using a 5-point Likert scale where five represented the highest rating.

Phase 2: Utilization of Summative Assessment

A letter has been sent to the Schools Division of Quezon, Public Schools District Supervisors, School Heads, Teachers, and Parents of the pupils involved to ask permission to conduct the study. The researcher administered the test on March 6-17, 2023. Moreover, the researcher explained and instructed the respondents for proper guidance in answering the instrument. After administering the summative assessment, the researcher analyzed and examined the outcomes of the respondents to evaluate and assess the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The data collected underwent statistical analysis to address the study questions. Descriptive statistics, such as frequency of responses, mean, and standard deviation, were employed to analyze the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills. Meanwhile, the mean percentage score was used to assess and evaluate the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science, based on the results of the administered summative assessment. Furthermore, a simple linear regression was calculated to determine the significant effect of the practices applied by Grade 6 educators on the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science. In regression analysis, a p-value (typically < 0.05) indicates the statistical significance of the independent variable (practices applied by Grade 6 educators) on the dependent variable (performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science).

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The primary objective of the study is to determine the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills at San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon during the 2022-2023 school year. Among the teachers' and pupils' enrollment, the researcher only involved the Grade 6 teachers and Grade 6 pupils. Furthermore, to examine the teaching practices of Grade 6 educators, the researcher surveyed 20 school heads and 39 Grade 6 teachers.

Additionally, 634 Grade 6 learners were included in the research to assess performance levels in Science. In total, there were 693 respondents. This investigation predicts the introduction of higher-order thinking skills into Grade 6 learning competencies. Thus, the researcher interviewed about the experiences of Grade 6 teachers in promoting HOTS in all learning areas. The interview results revealed that the Science subject has the most significant impact in promoting HOTS.

RESULTS

Part I. Practices Applied by Grade 6 Educators in Fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-Century Skills

Table 1.1

Practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills in terms of learning and innovation skills.

Indicators	School Heads			Grade 6 Teachers			Total		
	Mean	SD	DI	Mean	SD	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. The teacher inculcates contextualization in presenting the lesson/topic to spark the pupil's imagination.	4.15	0.59	OA	4.44	0.60	AA	4.29	0.59	AA
2. The teacher encourages the pupils to brainstorm to create new and worthwhile ideas.	4.15	0.59	OA	4.41	0.68	AA	4.28	0.63	AA
3. The teacher uses available learning materials to trigger the pupil's ability to demonstrate inventiveness and originality in work and understand the real-world limits to adopting new ideas.	4.20	0.41	AA	4.49	0.60	AA	4.34	0.51	AA
4. The teacher gives cases or situations that promote various types of reasoning, such as inductive and deductive.	4.25	0.44	AA	4.59	0.64	AA	4.42	0.54	AA
5. The teacher presents topics/ideas that enhance the ability of the pupils to analyze how parts of a whole interact with each other to produce overall outcomes in complex systems.	4.40	0.50	AA	4.49	0.56	AA	4.44	0.53	AA
6. The teacher allows the pupils to reflect critically on their learning experiences during the teaching and learning processes.	4.20	0.83	AA	4.44	0.60	AA	4.32	0.72	AA

7. The teacher integrates real-life situations to help the pupils solve different kinds of non-familiar problems in both conventional and innovative ways.	4.25	0.44	AA	4.67	0.53	AA	4.46	0.49	AA
8. The teacher gives cases or situations that promote communication for various purposes, such as to inform, instruct, motivate, and persuade.	4.10	0.31	OA	4.41	0.64	AA	4.26	0.47	AA
9. The teacher motivates the pupils to utilize media and technologies to communicate effectively in diverse environments.	3.85	0.93	OA	4.21	0.70	AA	4.03	0.81	OA
10. The teacher provides exercises requiring pupils to demonstrate their ability to work effectively and respectfully with diverse teams.	4.30	0.57	AA	4.33	0.66	AA	4.32	0.62	AA
Composite Mean	4.19	0.56	OA	4.45	0.62	AA	4.32	0.59	AA

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79 *Almost Not Applied (ANA)*
1.80 – 2.59 *Poorly Applied (PA)*
2.60 – 3.39 *Sometimes Applied (SA)*
3.40 – 4.19 *Often Applied (OA)*
4.20 – 5.00 *Always Applied (AA)*

Table 1.2

Practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills in terms of information, media, and technology skills.

Indicators	School Heads			Grade 6 Teachers			Total		
	Mean	SD	DI	Mean	SD	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. The teacher uses ICT equipment to enhance the ability of the pupils to access information (effectively and efficiently) and evaluate information (critically and competently).	3.80	0.77	OA	4.13	0.73	OA	3.96	0.75	OA
2. The teacher encourages the pupils to utilize online resources to understand better the ethical/legal issues surrounding the access and use of information.	3.55	0.83	OA	3.92	0.74	OA	3.74	0.78	OA
3. The teacher provides educational websites to help the pupils manage the flow of information from various sources.	3.15	0.88	SA	3.56	0.88	OA	3.36	0.88	SA
4. The teacher integrates issues or problems in the lesson to help the pupils use information accurately and creatively.	3.80	0.41	OA	4.26	0.68	AA	4.03	0.54	OA
5. The teacher makes use of online and offline platforms to examine how the pupils interpret messages differently.	3.75	0.79	OA	3.67	0.90	OA	3.71	0.84	OA
6. The teacher utilizes multiple software in enhancing how the pupils utilize the most appropriate media creation tools, expressions, and interpretations in diverse, multicultural environments.	3.10	0.72	SA	3.59	0.97	OA	3.34	0.84	SA
7. The teacher allows multimedia resources to help the pupils understand how and why media messages are constructed and for what purposes.	3.80	0.62	OA	3.95	0.76	OA	3.87	0.69	OA
8. The teacher uses school equipment and properties related to ICT to help the pupils use digital technologies to access, manage, integrate, evaluate, and create information to function successfully in a knowledge economy.	4.10	0.85	OA	4.05	0.86	OA	4.08	0.85	OA
9. The teacher teaches the use of technology in the teaching and learning process as a tool to research, organize, evaluate, and communicate information.	3.85	0.88	OA	4.13	0.70	OA	3.99	0.79	OA
10. The teacher allots time for hands-on activities for the pupils to enhance their ICT skills.	3.60	0.94	OA	3.56	0.85	OA	3.58	0.90	OA
Composite Mean	3.65	0.77	OA	3.88	0.81	OA	3.77	0.79	OA

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79 Almost Not Applied (ANA)

1.80 – 2.59 Poorly Applied (PA)

2.60 – 3.39 Sometimes Applied (SA)

3.40 – 4.19 Often Applied (OA)

4.20 – 5.00 Always Applied (AA)

Table 1.3

Practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills in terms of life and career skills.

Indicators	School Heads			Grade 6 Teachers			Total		
	Mean	SD	DI	Mean	SD	DI	Mean	SD	DI
1. The teacher motivates and engages the pupils through role-playing that aims to adapt to varied roles, job responsibilities, schedules, and contexts.	4.10	0.55	OA	4.41	0.75	AA	4.26	0.65	AA
2. The teacher integrates social values into the teaching and learning process to positively deal with praise, setbacks, and criticism.	4.25	0.44	AA	4.51	0.60	AA	4.38	0.52	AA
3. The teacher provides activities that require my pupils to set their personal goals (short-term and long-term) with the efficient use of time and workload management.	4.05	0.51	OA	4.49	0.56	AA	4.27	0.53	AA
4. The teacher seeks the help of the parents to encourage the pupils to demonstrate commitment to learning as a lifelong process.	4.20	0.70	AA	4.51	0.72	AA	4.36	0.71	AA
5. The teacher integrates values in the lessons/topics to enhance the ability of the pupils to conduct themselves in a respectable, professional manner.	4.55	0.51	AA	4.62	0.54	AA	4.58	0.53	AA
6. The teacher leverages social and cultural differences to help the pupils create new ideas and increase both innovation and quality of work.	4.35	0.67	AA	4.31	0.61	AA	4.33	0.64	AA
7. The teacher posts regularly the achievements and outcomes of the pupils to motivate them to prioritize, planning, and managing work to achieve the intended result.	4.35	0.67	AA	4.41	0.59	AA	4.38	0.63	AA
8. The teacher uses interpersonal and problem-solving skills to influence and guide the pupils toward a goal.	4.25	0.55	AA	4.49	0.68	AA	4.37	0.62	AA
9. The teacher integrates gestures in implementing class rules that the pupils can use in leading others in different activities.	4.25	0.64	AA	4.54	0.55	AA	4.39	0.60	AA
10. The teacher emphasizes the important role of each one to act responsibly with the interests of the larger community in mind before and after the conduct of electing class officers.	4.40	0.60	AA	4.54	0.55	AA	4.47	0.58	AA
Composite Mean	4.28	0.58	AA	4.48	0.62	AA	4.38	0.60	AA

Legend: 1.00 – 1.79 Almost Not Applied (ANA)

1.80 – 2.59 Poorly Applied (PA)

2.60 – 3.39 Sometimes Applied (SA)

3.40 – 4.19 Often Applied (OA)

4.20 – 5.00 Always Applied (AA)

Table 1.4

Summary table of the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills.

Practices Applied	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Learning and Innovation Skills	4.32	Always Applied
Information, Media, and Technology Skills	3.77	Often Applied
Life and Career Skills	4.38	Always Applied
Grand Mean	4.16	Often Applied

Part II. Performance Level of Grade 6 Pupils in Science

Table 2

The performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science

School	Mean Percentage Score	Verbal Interpretation	Levels of Achievement				
			Outstanding	Very Satisfactory	Satisfactory	Fairly Satisfactory	Did Not Meet Expectations
A	64.77	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	5	5	2	27
B	56.44	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	1	1	25
C	33.71	Did Not Meet Expectations	1	0	0	0	20
D	53.36	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	0	0	25
E	41.55	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	1	0	30
F	42.60	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	0	1	19
G	56.07	Did Not Meet Expectations	1	0	1	0	25
H	72.75	Did Not Meet Expectations	3	2	6	1	12
I	52.27	Did Not Meet Expectations	6	1	2	1	5
J	45.33	Did Not Meet Expectations	1	0	0	0	11
K	48.22	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	0	1	17
L	29.61	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	0	0	31
M	51.00	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	0	0	16
N	41.09	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	0	0	11
O	38.50	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	0	0	32
P	53.32	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	1	3	49
Q	60.22	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	2	0	25
R	56.58	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	1	1	29
S	33.11	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	1	0	26
T	48.09	Did Not Meet Expectations	0	0	2	1	20
Grand Mean	48.89	Did Not Meet Expectations	12	8	23	12	455

Legend: 90% – 100% *Outstanding*
 85% – 89% *Very Satisfactory*
 80% – 84% *Satisfactory*
 75% – 79% *Fairly Satisfactory*
 Below 75% *Did Not Meet Expectations*

Part III. Significant Effects of the Practices Applied by Grade 6 Educators to the Performance Level of Grade 6 Pupils in Science along with Higher-Order Thinking Skills

Table 3

A statistical table showing the effects of the practices applied by the Grade 6 educators on the performance level of Grade 6 Pupils in Science

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i> -value
	<i>B</i>	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	39.651	15.460		2.565	.013
Practices	2.359	3.672	.085	.642	.523

a. Dependent Variable: Performance level of Grade 6 Pupils in Science

DISCUSSION

Part I. Practices Applied by Grade 6 Educators in Fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-Century Skills

Table 1.1

Practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills in terms of learning and innovation skills.

As portrayed in Table 1.1, it can be inferred that Grade 6 teachers generally consistently apply most indicators, and most respondents rated them as "always applied". Statistics indicate that most teachers consistently implement practices to foster Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) related to learning and innovation for 21st-century skills. The results are supported by a composite mean of 4.32. This consistent application may reflect a proactive approach towards equipping students with the cognitive abilities and innovative mindset necessary to thrive in today's rapidly evolving world.

The positive result regarding the teachers' consistent application of learning and innovation skills in the teaching and learning process may align with their adherence to the goal of education, particularly under the Republic Act No. 10533, or the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013. This legislation emphasizes the importance of providing quality education that promotes critical thinking, creativity, and innovation among

learners. This alignment could be attributed to their participation in School Learning Action Cells (SLAC), which develop and support teachers by nurturing their knowledge, attitudes, and competencies in curriculum, instruction, and assessment within their workstations, as outlined in DepEd Order No. 35 s 2016 titled “The Learning Action Cell as a K To 12 Basic Education Program School-Based Continuing Professional Development Strategy for the Improvement of Teaching and Learning”.

Moreover, the top indicator suggests that most teachers effectively incorporate real-life situations into their teaching practices, indicating their dedication to providing meaningful learning experiences that resonate with students’ lives and prepare them for future challenges.

The results can be associated with the influence of the educational theory of constructivism and the principles of experiential learning on teachers. Constructivism suggests that learners build knowledge through experiences and interactions, emphasizing the significance of connecting new information with existing knowledge. Similarly, the principles of experiential learning highlight the role of practical experiences in fostering deep understanding and critical thinking. By integrating real-life situations into teaching, teachers can offer opportunities for active learning and the development of problem-solving skills, thereby preparing students for real-world challenges.

Furthermore, the table indicates that teachers frequently engage students in analyzing how different components interact within complex systems and provide cases or situations that encourage various types of reasoning, including inductive and deductive reasoning. This instructional practice may be associated with the excellent implementation of teachers in strand 1.5 (Strategies for developing critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills) of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). Notably, the exceptional performance of teachers in this indicator may appear to directly correlate with the positive outcomes identified in the data.

On the other hand, one of the indicators has been verbally interpreted as often applied, indicating that some teachers only "often" motivate pupils to utilize media and technologies for effective communication in diverse environments. The limited integration of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) among teachers across disciplines could be a contributing factor to the observed result. ICT encompasses the use of media and technology in the teaching and learning process. However, in the K to 12 curriculum, the competencies of ICT are only taught for one quarter alongside entrepreneurship. This might explain why teachers frequently only encourage students to utilize media and technologies for effective communication in various environments.

This aligns with the conclusion of Hazar and Özkurt (2021) that despite students’ proficiency in digital contexts outside the curriculum, education should integrate technology into learning-teaching processes and curricula to teach students how to evaluate, interpret, and effectively use information.

Overall, Chiruguru (2020) emphasized the indispensability of Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS), critical thinking, creative thinking, collaboration, and communication (4Cs) in teaching and learning for the 21st century. These skills are deemed essential daily and are encompassed within the realm of Higher-Order Thinking

Skills (HOTS). Students exposed to these 4Cs have demonstrated their effectiveness through their mastery of content and problem-solving abilities.

Table 1.2

Practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills in terms of information, media, and technology skills.

Table 1.2 shows that the majority of teachers frequently implement practices to foster Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) related to information, media, and technology for 21st-century skills. This is supported by a composite mean of 3.77. It may suggest that teachers have limited access to technology resources or training opportunities, which could hinder their ability to integrate 21st-century skills into their teaching practices consistently.

The absence of Information and Communications Technology (ICT) tools and equipment available for teachers to utilize in the teaching and learning process may be a contributing factor to the observed outcome. Despite the Department of Education's initiatives to supply public schools with suitable technologies to improve the teaching-learning process through the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP), reports indicate incomplete implementation of the program due to equipment shortages, inadequate training for implementers, and limited community understanding of effective computer utilization.

Herdina and Ningrum (2023) supported this claim by pointing out that teachers encounter various challenges in integrating technology into their teaching practices, including the lack of technology media facilities, slow internet connections, insufficient mastery of technological skills, and low motivation among teachers or students to utilize technology, along with inadequate preparation of materials.

Similarly, Akram et al. (2022) outlined several barriers hindering effective technology integration in teaching and learning, including resource constraints, lack of leadership support, accessibility issues with ICT infrastructure, time constraints, unclear policies, inadequate professional development, and insufficient technical support.

Upon closer examination of the table, specific indicators yielded lower mean scores, indicating sporadic application. For instance, teachers occasionally provide educational websites to help students manage information from various sources, and they sometimes utilize multiple software tools to enhance students' media creation skills and interpretations in diverse, multicultural settings.

The observed results could correlate with the results of the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form – Development Plan (IPCRF-DP) of teachers, which showed that many teachers have identified developmental needs in strand 1.3 (positive use of ICT) and strand 4.5 (teaching and learning resources including ICT) of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). This correlation clarifies why

teachers frequently provide educational websites and occasionally utilize multiple software tools.

Sera-Sirven (2021) supported this claim by emphasizing that while teachers may demonstrate familiarity with technology, this does not necessarily mean they are prepared to provide professional development and training on strategies for implementing new technology in classrooms. The lack of knowledge about new technology may leave teachers feeling ineffective.

Similarly, Molina (2021) added that these challenges persist because teachers are not adequately trained to incorporate technology into their instructional approaches, especially when working with culturally and linguistically diverse students. Furthermore, difficulties arise when students lack proficiency in using technology.

Table 1.3

Practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills in terms of life and career skills.

Table 1.3 indicates that most teachers consistently implement practices to foster Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) related to life and career for 21st-century skills. It is supported by a composite mean of 4.38. It may simply mean that life and career skills contain the essential knowledge and abilities needed by students to function in a variety of complex environments.

This implication may be associated with the adherence of teachers in the implementation of the Youth Formation Division (YFD) across the Department of Education. YFD emphasizes the development of life and career skills among learners, aiming to cultivate proactive Filipino youth who understand the importance of societal collaboration and addressing national aspirations.

Through these efforts, YFD not only nurtures academic excellence but also equips learners with essential life and career skills necessary for personal and professional success. By emphasizing holistic development and providing opportunities for engagement in crucial advocacy areas, YFD ensures that Filipino youth are well-prepared to contribute meaningfully to society and pursue fulfilling careers.

The top indicators suggest that most teachers prioritize integrating values, responsible citizenship, and leadership development in their teaching practices. They achieve this by incorporating values into lessons to promote respectful and professional behavior among students. Additionally, teachers emphasize the importance of responsible decision-making with the broader community's interests in mind, particularly evident during class officer elections.

The results may reflect the dedication of teachers to aligning with the mission, vision, and core values of the Department of Education. Mission and vision statements serve as concise, inspiring guides that effectively communicate the organization's direction and values. Core values further reinforce this sense of purpose and direction for

children, empowering them to make informed decisions and navigate difficult situations more effectively.

In line with this perspective, Chaiyama and Kaewpila (2022) underscored the necessity of transforming teaching practices to enhance the quality of individuals for the demands of the 21st century. This transformation entails integrating life and career skills into educational institutions at all levels, aiming not only to address daily challenges and meet employers' expectations but also to facilitate holistic development that empowers learners with versatile skills. Ensuring teachers' preparedness is crucial as it directly influences students' quality and readiness to navigate the dynamic world.

Furthermore, the findings indicated that teachers incorporate gestures into classroom rules to cultivate students' leadership skills, enhancing their capacity to lead others in various activities. These indicators may reflect teachers' dedication to fostering character development, promoting civic responsibility, and nurturing student leadership attributes.

The findings may be linked to the support provided by the Student Government Program (SPG) of the Department of Education, as outlined in DepEd Order No. 47, s. 2014. DepEd recognizes the SPG, specifically through the Supreme Elementary Learner Government (SELG), as a means to cultivate effective leadership among learners, contributing to their holistic development. The support given by DepEd explains why teachers consistently integrate these into the teaching and learning process.

This proactive approach by teachers in preparing students for success in an ever-changing society is consistent with the emphasis of Olorunfemi (2023) on the significance of life and career skills in today's rapidly evolving world. By imparting and acquiring these skills, individuals enhance their adaptability and flexibility, become influential leaders and responsible citizens, develop self-directed learning abilities, and bolster their proficiency in communication and collaboration. Whether in personal or professional realms, these skills are indispensable for navigating the complexities of the 21st century.

Table 1.4

Summary table of the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills.

Table 1.4 presents the summary table of the practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills in terms of learning and innovation skills, information, media, and technology skills; life and career skills as observed by school heads and evaluated by grade 6 teachers. The data from the table indicate that Grade 6 educators often apply practices that foster HOTS in Science for 21st-century skills, yielding a grand mean of 4.16.

The results may suggest that the practices applied by Grade 6 educators regarding information, media, and technology skills, which obtained the lowest mean score of 3.77, interpreted as "often applied," contribute to their frequent implementation. These findings could be linked to the challenges faced by teachers in integrating Information and

Communication Technology (ICT) into the teaching and learning process. These challenges may stem from teachers' capabilities in utilizing ICT positively and effectively incorporating teaching and learning resources, including ICT tools. Therefore, addressing these challenges is essential to ensure the seamless and effective integration of information, media, and technology skills into teachers' instructional practices.

Dyhrkopp (2021) emphasized that the use of technology in the classroom is essential due to the globalized world we now live in. Students must be prepared for future jobs that may not yet exist, rather than focusing solely on traditional roles. They need to develop skills in creating, collaborating, and effectively solving problems. Integrating technology into classrooms allows teachers to prepare students effectively for future success.

Moreover, Olorunfemi (2023) expanded on this by stating that in the modern era of digital communication, literacy skills extend beyond reading and writing to adeptly navigating and comprehending information, media, and technology. Effective communication now heavily relies on proficient technology use, highlighting the need to master digital literacy alongside traditional literacy skills.

Overall, Pangabebean et al. (2021) concluded that the importance of not only comprehending the concept of 21st-century learning skills but also effectively implementing them in educational practices. It underscores the necessity of active involvement from all stakeholders within the educational setting for the successful integration of these skills to enhance HOTS among students. Schools, as formal educational institutions, play a pivotal role in initiating change, with teachers at the forefront. They must not only grasp the significance of these skills but also translate them into actionable strategies in their planning, execution, and assessment of learning activities.

Part II. Performance Level of Grade 6 Pupils in Science

Table 2

The performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science

Table 2 presents the mean percentage scores, verbal interpretations, and summary of Grade 6 pupils' performance level in Science. The table shows that there were 12 outstanding pupils, 8 very satisfactory pupils, 23 satisfactory pupils, 12 fairly satisfactory pupils, and 455 pupils who did not meet expectations. Overall, the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science across 20 elementary schools in San Narciso Districts, Division of Quezon obtained a grand mean of 48.89 which is verbally interpreted as did not meet expectations.

The findings are consistent with research conducted in Indonesia by Pangabebean et al. (2021), which identified several factors contributing to students' low quality and achievement, including a lack of training in solving contextual problems and insufficient

emphasis on reasoning, argumentation, and creativity in teaching practices. Additionally, Ihsan et al. (2020) noted that teachers often prioritize lower-order learning over higher-order thinking skills in their Science instruction.

Similarly, Otgonbaatar (2020) concluded that students are inadequately trained in addressing items requiring higher-order thinking. This deficiency may stem from factors such as unfamiliarity with item formats and question types, as well as a lack of exposure to demanding higher-order thinking activities in Mongolian primary schools.

Overall, Suseelan et al. (2023) proposed a shift in teaching approaches, advocating for a greater emphasis on problem-solving skills and the implementation of educational interventions aimed at enhancing students' problem-solving abilities across all school settings.

Based on the data from various studies, it is evident that significant challenges exist in the education system concerning the development and application of Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) among students. This challenge may stem partly from the prevalent emphasis on rote memorization over critical thinking in teaching practices, alongside a lack of teacher training in integrating HOTS into lessons. Moreover, students' limited exposure to challenging higher-order thinking activities may worsen the issue. Addressing these challenges necessitates systemic reforms in curriculum design, teacher training, and classroom practices to prioritize the cultivation of critical thinking skills essential for success in the modern world.

Part III. Significant Effects of the Practices Applied by Grade 6 Educators to the Performance Level of Grade 6 Pupils in Science along with Higher-Order Thinking Skills

Table 3

A statistical table showing the effects of the practices applied by the Grade 6 educators on the performance level of Grade 6 Pupils in Science

Table 3 shows that the practices applied by Grade 6 educators have no significant effect on the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science ($p = 0.523 > 0.05$). The results may indicate that despite the efforts of educators to instill Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) among Grade 6 pupils, the study revealed that their practices had no significant effect.

Thus, further analysis may be necessary to understand why the teachers' practices did not yield significant results. It could be beneficial to investigate the teachers' capabilities in instilling HOTS, the alignment of assessment tools with Higher-Order Thinking objectives, the level of student engagement, or other practices that may influence the effectiveness of fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills in Science for 21st-century skills.

Kurniawan (2020) underscored the ongoing issue concerning teachers' comprehension and familiarity with HOTS. A significant portion of teachers exhibited only a rudimentary understanding of HOTS concepts and harbored misconceptions regarding critical components. The primary challenge for these educators was instructing topics they did not fully grasp and imparting skills they had not yet mastered to their students. Teachers lacking a solid grasp of HOTS may struggle to teach HOTS-related content effectively, consequently impacting their ability to cultivate HOTS skills among students. Therefore, educators must adopt teaching methods and utilize the cognitive tools recommended by the Ministry of Education and Culture to address this challenge.

Additionally, a study by Antara and Dewantara (2022) highlighted various obstacles faced by both learners and teachers. Students often lack training in addressing HOTS-related questions, while teachers may struggle with fostering HOTS-oriented learning activities.

Furthermore, Wahyuni and Supriatna (2022) emphasized the critical role of teachers in shaping the educational process and outcomes. The quality of learning outcomes is intricately linked to the quality and complexity of questions crafted and analyzed by teachers. In this era, educators must possess the capability to formulate and refine HOTS-based questions that not only assess memory recall but also evaluate, create, analyze, and foster critical thinking skills.

Part IV. Proposed Intervention Program

Based on the study's findings, the researcher developed an intervention program titled "Empowering Grade 6 Science: Cultivating Higher-Order Thinking Skills Through Innovative Pedagogy" to address the identified gaps. The intervention program's components are carefully designed to address the identified needs and challenges in Grade 6 Science education.

Professional development workshops are deemed essential to equip Grade 6 educators with targeted training in integrating information communication technology (ICT) effectively. These workshops aim to bridge the gap identified in ICT integration, empowering educators to leverage digital resources and multimedia presentations to enhance Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) development in Science for 21st-century skills. Additionally, emphasizing inquiry-based learning approaches is crucial to better prepare students for contextual challenges of the 21st-century education that demands creativity, critical thinking, and sound judgment.

Student engagement initiatives, such as hands-on experiments and project-based learning tasks, are also indispensable to foster curiosity and enthusiasm for Science among Grade 6 pupils, addressing the shortfall in student performance and engagement identified in the study.

Furthermore, assessment development workshops are necessary to improve assessment practices and accurately measure student mastery of HOTS in Science. By

designing HOTS-based assessments and rubrics, educators can gather valuable insights into student progress and tailor instruction to meet individual learning needs, ultimately fostering the development of HOTS for 21st-century skills. A comprehensive detail about the proposed intervention program is provided in Appendix A."

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following were concluded:

1. The practices applied by Grade 6 educators in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills were often applied. Moreover, the domain of information, media, and technology attained the lowest mean score. The results suggest that teachers frequently integrate information communication technology into the teaching and learning process.
2. The performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science falls below 75% or fails to meet expectations. The results suggest that these learners may lack training in tackling contextual challenges that demand creativity, critical thinking, and sound judgment.
3. The null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that the practices applied by grade 6 educators in areas like learning and innovation skills, information, media, and technology skills, as well as life and career skills, do not have a significant effect on the performance level of Grade 6 pupils in Science. The results suggest that the existing practices applied by the Grade 6 educators cannot foster HOTS.
4. The researcher developed an intervention program that introduces new practices to Grade 6 educators. These practices aim to effectively foster HOTS among Grade 6 pupils and consequently improve their performance level in Science.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions drawn, the following recommendations are presented:

For the DepEd Officials and Authorities

- Consider expanding research initiatives to delve deeper into the specific areas where Grade 6 educators excel or struggle in fostering Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science, particularly in addressing the domain of information, media, and technology skills.
- Advocate for professional development programs that focus on enhancing educators' abilities to integrate Information and Communication Technology (ICT) effectively into the teaching and learning process.

For the District Supervisors

- Collaborate with schools to implement targeted interventions aimed at improving students' proficiency in Science, with a particular emphasis on addressing the identified areas of weakness, such as creativity, critical thinking, and sound judgment.
- Facilitate opportunities for teachers to share best practices and strategies for fostering HOTS in Science, including the effective integration of technology into instruction.

For the School Heads

- Provide support and resources to teachers to strengthen their instructional practices in fostering HOTS in Science, particularly in addressing the identified areas of improvement, such as information, media, and technology skills.
- Allocate resources for the acquisition and maintenance of ICT tools and resources to support teaching and learning.

For the Teachers

- Ensure that HOTS-based questions are open-ended to promote critical thinking and problem-solving skills among students.
- Participate in ongoing professional development opportunities to enhance their capacity to effectively integrate HOTS development into Science instruction, focusing on addressing the identified areas of weakness.
- Collaborate with colleagues to share effective practices and resources for integrating technology into classroom instruction.

For the Future Researchers

- Extend research efforts to explore the factors influencing the effectiveness of interventions aimed at fostering HOTS in Science among Grade 6 pupils, including the role of teacher training, classroom practices, and student engagement.
- Investigate potential policy implementations at the national and local levels to support educators in effectively integrating information communication technology into Science instruction and promoting 21st-century skills development.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In researching the practices of Grade 6 educators to foster Higher-Order Thinking Skills (HOTS) in Science for 21st-century skills, the researcher conducted the study strictly adhering to ethics so that there would be no harm of any kind to the human respondents.

The researcher obtained their full consent regarding the purpose, procedures, and possible risks of the study. The researcher made sure that any withdrawal from the study at any point would not have any recourse or repercussion, and the researcher ensured that at all times, the autonomy of the participants and their comfort became paramount.

Also, the researcher ensured the identity of the respondents by concealing their names and information disclosed in the course of this study to protect their anonymity. Additionally, the researcher considered the respondent's welfare in the course of the study and beyond when engaging them in the study to ensure that they have no chance of getting more distressed or harmed.

Research was undertaken without any conflict of interest; hence, the integrity and impartiality of the research were not compromised in any way. The researcher was not plagiarizing and cited everything appropriately to maintain the integrity of the work and avoid plagiarism. As a means of bias prevention, the interpretation was submitted to diligence. The researcher analyzed these results objectively and accurately.

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